

Unlock the power of open science data

FACTSHEET FOR DEVELOPERS, SERVICE PROVIDERS, RESEARCHERS, RESEARCH MANAGERS AND POLICY MAKERS

What is it?

OpenAIRE Research Graph (<https://graph.openaire.eu>) is an open resource that aggregates a collection of research data properties (metadata, links) available within the OpenAIRE Open Science infrastructure for funders, organizations, researchers, research communities and publishers to interlink information by using a semantic graph database approach.

How it works

Aggregation

OpenAIRE aggregates metadata records describing objects of the research life-cycle from content providers compliant to the OpenAIRE guidelines, from entity registries, and from other relevant data sources (not compliant to the guidelines) like Crossref, and ORCID.

Enrichment by mining

The OpenAIRE Graph is enriched by links mined by OpenAIRE's full-text mining algorithms that scan the full texts of publications searching, among others, for funding information, references to datasets, software URIs, accession numbers of bioentities, and European Patent Office (EPO) mentions.

Deduplication

Different records representing the same entity and metadata records corresponding to equivalent objects, collected from different data sources, are merged. The deduplication process is applied to research results, data sources, and organisations.

How we build it?

OpenAIRE Graph How it works (cont.)

Enrichment by inference

Results that meet certain criteria (defined by community managers) are associated with the respective communities (deduction process). New links and/or new properties are also added to the Graph, exploiting existing semantic relationships and values between the involved entities (propagation process).

Finalisation

Final cleaning step to harmonise values according to controlled vocabularies. The output of this final cleansing step is the final version of the OpenAIRE Graph.

For developers

Start building with OpenAIRE APIs

Not sure where to start?

Let us give you some guides and reference documentation.

Know more about how we build it

<https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/graph-production-workflow/>

Metadata dumps

<https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/category/downloads/>

Data model

<https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/data-model/>

OpenAIRE APIs

<https://graph.openaire.eu/develop/api.html>

About OpenAIRE

www.openaire.eu

Shifting scholarly communication towards openness and transparency and facilitate innovative ways to communicate and monitor research.

For more information, please contact: info@openaire.eu

Additional Guidance: www.openaire.eu/guides

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We believe in numbers

26 Funders

131K Data Sources

3M Projects

167M publications

59M research data

202K research software

8M other research outputs

Major contributors

Benefits for all kind of users

For Researchers

Intelligent and contextual discovery of research:

- Open Access versions
- Navigation through publication, data and software
- Discovery of data and software

For Service Providers

Contribute to and use the graph for new services:

- Metadata and collections interoperable
- Research Graph dump and APIs
- New services

For Research managers & Policy makers

Used in metrics:

- Open Science trends
- Compliance to funder mandates
- Research Impact

Useful Links

OpenAIRE Graph Webpage

<https://graph.openaire.eu>

Documentation

<https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/>

Beginner's Kit

<https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/downloads/beginners-kit/>

This factsheet is also available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8056366>